

**DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL CHILDREN
THROUGH CREATIVE WRITING.**

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Annotation: This article gives information how to improve linguistic competence of school children through creative writing. It considers the relevance of creative writing in language development while emphasising the role of this type of writing in personal development through boosting imagination, creative thinking, self-esteem and the ability to find original solutions. The article sets out to identify skills required to ensure productive creative writing, addresses various approaches towards defining creativity and compares creative writing to expository writing.

Key words: linguistic, creative writing, creative thinking, creativity, imagination, expository writing, school curriculum, academic competitions.

Linguistic skills measure the capacity of individuals to understand and express themselves, both in written and oral form. When we learn a language, there are four skills that we need for complete communication. When we learn our native language, we usually learn to **listen** first, then to **speak**, then to **read**, and finally to **write**. These are called the four "linguistic skills"(writing,listening, reading, speaking).

While communication employs both oral and written language, the latter is a challenging task for L2 learners for a number of reasons, including 'permanence and

distance of writing, coupled with its unique rhetorical conventions¹. To master the writing process, students should adopt a thorough approach involving adequate planning, composing, evaluating, revising and editing. The complexity of written production results in teachers encountering a set of problems, such as lack of motivation, interest, or effort, as well as increased levels of anxiety and procrastination. Therefore, writing presents difficulties from the student-teacher perspective. Teachers have to employ appropriate resources, set clear objectives, provide learners with clear guidance and create certain stimuli and conditions ensuring successful writing practice, while it is imperative for students to understand the different steps that underpin text production. The creative writing approach is sometimes viewed as a remedy to the above listed problems since it has the potential to promote inspiration, motivation and imagination through unlocking students' individuality. Also, it helps render the learning process more enjoyable and stimulating.² Creative thinking and creativity are known to form the basis of creative writing, which is often regarded as imaginative and inspiring written products, normally taking the form of fiction and poetry. There exist two propositions concerning whether creativity and creative writing can be taught, which will be addressed later in the article.

Writing is viewed as one of the most difficult skills to acquire while learning a foreign language due to its complex nature and the number of skills needed in order to use written language effectively. It involves a wide range of abilities such as using cognitive, affective, social and psychomotor skills. Writing activities also require numerous skills ranging from lower level (spelling, pronunciation and word choice)

¹ Maxmudova, N. (2021). LEXICAL-SEMANTIC GROUP OF ORNITHONYMS IN LANGUAGE AND THEIR USE. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(5), 107-116.

² Abbasova, N. K. (2019). The importance of techniques in developing critical abilities of the learners in teaching English proverbs and sayings. *Мировая наука*, (9), 3-6.

to highly complex skills such as planning and structuring a text along with generating and organising ideas. According to Maley (2015), language teachers can also benefit greatly from incorporating creative writing in the curriculum since:

- it stimulates professional development (through enhancing teachers' language skills, making teachers serve as role models and providing new insights into teaching writing);

it contributes to personal growth;

- it allows a more efficient materials presentation;
- it diversifies lessons by offering solutions to organising the lesson in terms of its content.

Creative writing plays a significant role in the learning process since it has the potential to diversify it through a range of creative activities offered to students. Not only does it aid language development (including grammar and vocabulary) but it also contributes to personal growth. This type of writing is proven to stimulate imagination and inventiveness, boost self-esteem and raise selfconfidence, so that students are more eager to express their identity and find original solutions.³ Consequently, it makes the learning process more person-oriented, inasmuch as it motivates students to express their own voices and thoughts in written texts. A lack of strict schemata and rules, which overwhelm academic writing (essays, reports, etc.), eventually stimulates students to think independently and freely. Therefore, being of substantial educational value, creative writing should be incorporated in the school curriculum and taught on a regular basis. Creative writing has a long-term perspective since it helps develop creative personalities characterised by flexible thinking, independence of views, high productivity and originality. These are the skills needed in every occupation.

1. ³ Dilnozakhon, Y. (2022). TEACHING PRAGMATICS BY EXPRESSING AND GIVING COMPLIMENTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 575-578.

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